

Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge and Instructional Practices of Public-School Elementary Teachers in Matina District

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Abstract. The study examined the relationship between technological pedagogical content knowledge and instructional practices of teachers in public elementary schools of Matina District, Davao City Division. Also, it investigated the association of the involved variables and the domains of technological pedagogical content knowledge that significantly influence the instructional practices of teachers. With the use of probability sampling, 111 public elementary teachers were selected as the respondents. Utilizing the descriptive-correlational survey method, the data collated were analyzed through the use of Mean, Product-Moment correlation, and Regression Analysis. Results revealed that there was a high technological pedagogical content knowledge and high instructional practices of teachers. Furthermore, there was a significant relationship between the two variables. Moreover, all domains of technological pedagogical content knowledge were found to have a significant influence on the instructional practices of teachers. Based on the findings, it was further suggested that higher officials in the Department of Education and school heads may work together in crafting more programs and interventions that would intensify the technological pedagogical content knowledge, which would pave the way to more effective instructional practices of teachers. Moreover, future researchers may further explore the involved variables, considering other factors and research methods.

KEY WORDS

1. Technological pedagogical content knowledge
2. instructional practices
3. Davao City Division

Date Received: May 05, 2025 — Date Reviewed: June 15, 2025 — Date Published: July 12, 2025

1. Introduction

Specific instructional practices guided effective teaching. These instructional practices are a set of teaching strategies and methods of instruction employed by the teacher in the classroom to achieve the desired teaching and learning objectives. Saleh and Jing (2020) defined instructional practices as the actions made by teachers in producing the lesson in the classroom. How the teachers plan their instructions into a sequence of events - presenting the lesson, asking questions, demonstrating skills, and evaluating performance are all parts of their instructional practices. However, teaching is one of the most demanding professions out there. Teachers are constantly working to juggle all their tasks of educating students, managing behavior, completing administrative tasks, and more. With the high demand from all their job

responsibilities, teachers commonly experience burnout. Hence, they tend to feel drained after working on lesson plans, tend to dread going to work, and lack the motivation to be productive (Hegwood, 2023). The ripple effects of poor instructional practices were a global concern, undermining the foundation of quality education and the potential of future generations worldwide. In India, most teachers cannot think critically and problem-solve regarding teaching methods, content, and organization. The curriculum of the teacher-education program must undergo comprehensive reform and reorganization in response to the ever-changing needs of society (Amirrudin, 2023). In Africa, teachers in rural areas are not inclined to integrate digital technology into teaching and learning. Several reasons have been suggested as to why teachers do not integrate digital technology into their routine instruction, such as teachers' attitudes, lack of technological skills to integrate technology into practice, and lack of effective or adequate professional development (Walan, 2020). In Pakistan, monitoring the quality of teaching practices of primary school teachers in low-and middle-income countries is often hampered by the lack of freely available classroom observation tools that are feasible to administer, validated in their own setting, and can be used as part of national monitoring systems (Molina et al., 2020). In the Philippine context, Gumarang and Gumarang (2021) disclosed that three major problems in the Philippine education system such as overcrowded students in a classroom, teacher are teaching subjects that is not their expertise, and poor quality in instruction. Moreover, in the World Bank survey which is mentioned by Chi (2023) in the Philippine Star, it is revealed teachers' lack of mastery of what they teach and teacher absenteeism have contributed to the Philippines' high learning poverty, a new World Bank report found. Findings from a new World Bank report focusing on the East Asia and Pacific region found

that teachers in the Philippines have one of the most ineffective methods in Southeast Asia and teacher training programs targeted at them have failed to improve their mastery of content. Magallanes et al. (2022) also discovered that with the implementation of the K-12 curriculum, many teachers in the Philippines struggle to deliver the scope of class learning materials and possess poor teaching strategies and skills. Furthermore, Dizon, Calbi, Cuyos, and Miranda (2019) emphasized a lack of preparation for teaching development in the Philippines, making it necessary for teachers to be well-equipped with top-notch teaching strategies that maximize teacher-student participation. In the local context, the Division of Davao Del Norte is home to a large number of schools, many of which are situated in remote areas, including hilly areas. The majority of teachers in their assigned areas struggle to teach due to a lack of resources, accessibility issues, and inadequate macro skills. The teaching experiences are not one-size-fits-all; instead, every teacher faces unique challenges that they must overcome to provide their pupils with a well-rounded education (Algonos et al., 2024). In the Matina District, as observed by the researcher, the integration of Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) in instructional practices remains a significant challenge for teachers. Despite the increasing availability of digital tools and resources, many educators struggle to effectively align technology with pedagogical strategies and subject content, resulting in suboptimal teaching practices. Limited professional development opportunities, inadequate access to advanced technological tools, and varying levels of digital literacy among teachers exacerbate the issue. This disconnect not only hampers the potential for innovative and engaging learning experiences but also widens the gap in achieving educational outcomes aligned with 21st-century skills. Addressing this problem requires a comprehensive approach to enhance

teachers' competencies, promote collaborative learning environments, and ensure equitable access to technology across the district. While instructional practices had been widely studied as a cornerstone of effective teaching, a significant research gap existed in understanding how these practices evolve in response to contemporary educational challenges, such as diverse student needs, technological advancements, and curriculum reforms. Given that incorporating the use of technology was relevant to teachers' instructional practices. Hence, this study explored the status of technological pedagogical content knowledge and instructional practices of teachers. Investigating this relationship provided valuable insights into the strengths and challenges teachers encountered in applying their TPACK knowledge to real-world teaching scenarios. Such a study could identify best practices, inform targeted professional development programs, and guide policy reforms aimed at equipping educators with the skills needed to create dynamic, effective, and inclusive learning environments in today's technology-driven world. In this academic journey, the researcher intended to provide a deeper understanding of these variables, with a specific focus on public elementary teachers. Disseminating the findings of a study on Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) and instructional practices was crucial for maximizing its impact on education. This could be achieved by presenting the results at educational conferences, publishing in peer-reviewed journals, and creating accessible reports or infographics for teachers, school administrators, and policymakers.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study—This study was mainly anchored on the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge Framework by Mishra and Koeler (2006). This framework focuses on technological knowledge (TK), pedagogical knowledge (PK), and content knowledge (CK), and offers a productive approach to many of the

dilemmas that teachers face in implementing educational technology (edtech) in their classrooms. By differentiating among these three types of knowledge, the TPACK framework outlines how content (what is being taught) and pedagogy (how the teacher imparts that content) must form the foundation for any effective edtech integration. This order is important because the technology being implemented must communicate the content and support the pedagogy in order to enhance students' learning experience (Kurt, 2018). The framework focuses on designing and evaluating teacher knowledge that is concentrated on effective student learning in various content areas (AACTE Committee on Innovation and Technology, 2008). Thus, TPACK is a useful frame for thinking about what knowledge teachers must have to integrate technology into teaching and how they might develop this knowledge. Using TPACK as a framework for measuring teaching knowledge could potentially have an impact on the type of training and professional development experiences that are designed for both preservice and in-service teachers (Schmidt et al., 2009). The TPACK Framework is highly relevant to understanding the relationship between Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) and the instructional practices of teachers, as it provides a structured approach to integrating technology effectively into teaching. It emphasizes the interconnectedness of three core knowledge areas—content, pedagogy, and technology—and highlights how their synergy enhances instructional design and delivery. By applying the TPACK framework, teachers can make informed decisions on selecting and using digital tools that align with subject-specific content and pedagogical strategies, creating more engaging and effective learning experiences. This relevance is particularly critical in today's education landscape, where technology plays an integral role in addressing diverse learning needs and fostering student achievement. An-

other theory that supported this study is the Situated Learning Theory (SLT) by Lave and Wenger (1991). This theory highlighted the process and development of learning when individuals have the opportunity to participate in a community of practice. In such a community, new learners reach the level of an expert as they have more opportunities to practice within the context of learning. In this light, learning is unintentional; this unintentional nature of learning is what the authors call Legitimate Peripheral Participation (LPP). In LPP, the learner moves from the periphery of the community to the center as he/she gains expertise and engages and participates actively in the sociocultural practices of the community (Lave Wenger, 1991). In the context of this study, the theory was highly relevant to Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) and instructional practices because it emphasizes learning within authentic contexts and through active participation. This theory aligns with the TPACK framework by encouraging teachers to integrate technology into their pedagogy in ways that reflect real-world applications of knowledge. For instance, using digital tools to simulate real-life scenarios or collaborative platforms for problem-solving mirrors the authentic contexts where knowledge is applied. By situating learning in meaningful and practical contexts, teachers can enhance engagement, deepen understanding, and better equip students with skills for the modern world. This approach reinforces the idea that effective instructional practices must bridge theoretical knowledge with practical, technology-supported experiences. Figure 1 shows the conceptual model of the study. It focuses on

the level of technological pedagogical content knowledge and instructional practices of teachers. The independent variable is the technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge of teachers. It has three indicators, namely: technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, and content knowledge (Schmid, Brianza Petko, 2020). In this study, technological knowledge refers to a teacher's understanding of how to effectively use and integrate various technological tools and resources in the classroom to support teaching and enhance learning. Pedagogical knowledge refers to a teacher's understanding of effective teaching methods, strategies, and practices that can be applied to facilitate student learning and engagement in various instructional contexts. Content knowledge refers to a teacher's deep understanding of the subject matter they teach, including its concepts, theories, facts, and practices, which serves as the foundation for effective teaching and learning. Meanwhile, the dependent variable was the instructional practices of teachers. It has three indicators, namely: cognitive, interpersonal, and intrapersonal (Khanshan Yousefi, 2020). In this study, cognitive refers to the strategies that teachers use to engage students' thinking processes, such as problem-solving, critical thinking, and conceptual understanding. Interpersonal refers to the teacher's ability to build positive relationships with students, foster collaboration, and manage classroom dynamics. Intrapersonal refers to a teacher's self-awareness, emotional regulation, and reflective abilities, enabling them to adapt their teaching strategies, and maintain resilience in the face of challenges.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, a comprehensive outline is presented regarding the methodology employed in this study, covering aspects such as the research design, participants, tools, procedures for data collection, and the analysis methods to be applied throughout this investigation.

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

2.1. Research Design—This research adopted a quantitative approach, specifically using a descriptive correlational design. Quantitative research is centered on the collection and analysis of numerical data to investigate specific phenomena or behaviors within a defined group, known as the sample population. This method is commonly applied in social sciences, including communication studies, to systematically observe and measure various factors that influence individuals, with the aim of enhancing understanding of these influences. In particular, a descriptive correlational study focuses on identifying and describing the relationships between variables, without delving into causal connections or manipulations of those variables. Through this design, researchers seek to uncover patterns and trends that can contribute to a broader comprehension of the topic under study (Leedy Ormrod, 2019). In descriptive research, the researcher avoids altering variables, focusing instead on illustrating and detailing the characteristics and attributes of those variables. On the other hand, a correlational research design aims to examine the relationships between variables without attempting to manipulate them. This approach evaluates the strength and direction of these relationships, determining whether they are positive or negative and assessing whether they are strong or weak. Correlational studies help identify patterns and associations between variables, offering valuable insights into their interconnectedness without implying cause-and-effect relationships (Sreekumar, 2024). The study was considered descriptive correlational research because it sought to identify and describe the relationship between the integration of technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge in teaching without manipulating any of the variables. In this context, the study did not attempt to establish causality but focused on understanding how different aspects of teachers’ knowledge and instructional practices were

interconnected, determining if, and to what extent, certain technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge factors influence teaching practices. This approach provided valuable insights into how these elements coexist and affect instructional strategies.

2.2. Ethical Consideration—The ethical considerations for this study emphasized maintaining appropriate research practices while ensuring the confidentiality and anonymity of participants. These concerns were integral to the research methodology and aligned with the ethical guidelines. Key ethical aspects included protecting the privacy of participants, ensuring their voluntary participation, obtaining informed consent, and upholding the integrity of the data collection and analysis process. By adhering to these standards, the study safeguarded participants' rights and maintained the ethical integrity of the research.

2.3. Research Respondents—The study focused on 111 public elementary teachers in the Matina District. Using the Slovin Formula with a margin of error of 0.05, the total population of 155 Grade 6 teachers with at least two years of teaching experience was reduced to 111. This aligned with the standard guideline that at least 50 participants are required for simple regression analysis, and generally, 100 participants are considered sufficient for most research scenarios (Hair et al., 2018). Thus, including 111 respondents exceeded the necessary sample size, ensuring the study's objectives were met effectively. For this research, a probability sampling method was applied, specifically using a two-stage cluster sampling technique. This ensured that every individual in the population had a measurable chance of being included in the sample, thus providing equal and independent selection opportunities for all participants (Ragab Arisha, 2018). Cluster sampling, which is a common method in research, involves dividing the population into separate clusters, each consisting of unique units that collectively repre-

sent different subsets of the population (Thomas, 2020). In this study, the two-stage cluster sampling process involved randomly selecting elements from the clusters identified in the initial phase of the sampling process. The target group for this research consisted of all elementary teachers in the public schools of Matina District. This study focused on selecting elementary teachers with at least 2 years of teaching experience. This criterion was based on the understanding that teachers with this level of experience are better equipped to evaluate their own technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge as well as their instructional practices. Additionally, it would be important to note that participants had the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time if they felt uncomfortable with the survey. Their decision was fully respected, ensuring that the well-being of participants was prioritized throughout the research process.

2.4. Research Instrument—For data collection, this study employed an adapted survey questionnaire designed specifically for this research. The questionnaire was segmented into two distinct sets to thoroughly address the research objectives: the first set focused on evaluating the technological pedagogical content knowledge of teachers. At the same time, the second was dedicated to assessing the instructional practices of teachers.

Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge

The technological pedagogical content knowledge questionnaire was adapted from Schmid et al. (2020). The instrument consisted of 20 items. It has the following indicators, namely: technological knowledge (1-7), pedagogical knowledge (1-7), and content knowledge (1-6). The questionnaire was subjected to pilot testing to ensure the reliability of the tool. The next page was the rating scale of technological pedagogical content knowledge of teachers.

Scale Descriptive Levels and Interpretations for TPACK

Mean Interval	Descriptive Level	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	The technological pedagogical content knowledge of teachers is always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	High	The technological pedagogical content knowledge of teachers is oftentimes evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately High	The technological pedagogical content knowledge of teachers is occasionally evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	The technological pedagogical content knowledge of teachers is seldom evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	The technological pedagogical content knowledge of teachers is never evident.

Instructional Practices

The instructional practices questionnaire was adapted from Khanshan and Yousefi (2020). The instrument consisted of 36 items. It had the following indicators, namely: cognitive (1-18), interpersonal (1-10), and intrapersonal (1-8). The questionnaire was subjected to pilot testing to ensure the reliability of the tool. The next page was the rating scale of organizational learning. The research instrument for this study was thoughtfully developed to align with its specific objectives and goals. To ensure content

validity, the survey questionnaire was reviewed by three expert validators. The researcher incorporated feedback and suggestions from the advisor, panel members, and validators through a detailed review process. Following this, a pilot test was conducted with 30 public elementary school teachers who were not part of the study sample to assess the tool’s reliability. This iterative process was crucial for refining the instrument, ensuring that it accurately measured the intended constructs, and enhancing its validity and effectiveness in gathering relevant data.

Scale Descriptive Levels and Interpretations for Instructional Practices

Mean Interval	Descriptive Level	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	The instructional practices of teachers are always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	High	The instructional practices of teachers are oftentimes evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately High	The instructional practices of teachers are occasionally evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	The instructional practices of teachers are seldom evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	The instructional practices of teachers are never evident.

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—

In gathering the data, the researcher followed a strict procedure and protocol. All the data collected was systematically recorded, organized, and analyzed while maintaining confi-

2.6. Data Analysis—For more comprehensive interpretation and analysis of the data, the following statistical tools were utilized: Mean, Pearson r , and Regression Analysis. These methods were selected to ensure an in-depth and accurate analysis of the data in addressing the research questions. Mean This was used to measure the level of technological pedagogical

dentiality. The researcher worked closely with a statistician to ensure accurate data interpretation and that proper statistical procedures were followed throughout the analysis process.

content knowledge and instructional practices of teachers. Pearson R . This was utilized to determine the relationship between technological pedagogical content knowledge and instructional practices of teachers. Regression Analysis This was utilized to determine the significant influence of technological pedagogical content knowledge on instructional practices of teachers.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results of the study. These are the findings of the problems raised in the previous chapter. They are presented both in textual and tabular forms.

3.1. Level of Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Teachers—Summary on the Level of Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Teachers

Table 4 provides a summary of the level of technological pedagogical content knowledge of teachers. It is exhibited that the overall mean of personal qualities of teachers was 3.42, which was at a high level. This means that the technological pedagogical content knowledge of teachers was oftentimes evident. Data shows that the three (3) indicators have varying results ranging from moderately high to high levels. As arranged chronologically, pedagogical knowledge and content knowledge have the highest mean score (3.46). This is followed by technological knowledge (3.34). These serve as proof that the level of technological pedagogical content knowledge of teachers is often evident. The findings reveal that the overall level of Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) of teachers falls under the high-level category. This indicates that teachers often demonstrate integration of technology, peda-

gogy, and content in their instructional practices. The high overall mean reflects a solid foundation in the essential components of TPACK, suggesting that most teachers are capable of combining these areas to support effective teaching and learning. The findings affirm that TPACK is not only present but consistently evident in their professional practice, contributing to their overall instructional effectiveness. A closer look at the three core indicators shows varying strengths across the domains. Both pedagogical knowledge and content knowledge scored highest with a mean reflecting teachers' strong command of instructional strategies and subject matter expertise. On the other hand, technological knowledge scored lower which, although still within the moderately high range, suggests that technology integration is not as consistently evident as the other two components. This variation indicates that while teachers are confident in pedagogy and content, there may be a need for further support and training in effectively incorporating technology into their teaching. Strengthening this area could

help raise the overall TPACK level from often-times evident to consistently demonstrated. The high technological pedagogical content knowledge of teachers affirmed the ideas of Bueno et al. (2023) revealing that good teaching with technology, therefore, cannot be achieved by simply adding a new piece of technology upon existing structures. Good teaching, with technology, requires a shift in existing pedagogical and content domains. The TPACK framework also emphasizes the role of the context within teaching and learning occurs. Ignoring context leads to “generic solutions to the problem of teaching”. Mishra et al. (2022) highlighted that teaching is a context-bound activity, and teachers with developed TPACK use technology to design learning experiences tailored for specific pedagogies, crafted for specific content, as instantiated in specific learning contexts. In the

same vein, Soko and Samo (2023) claimed that the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework describes the type of teacher knowledge required to teach effectively with technology. Describing what teachers need to know can be difficult because teaching is an inherently complex, multifaceted activity that occurs in varied settings. By its nature, teaching is an ill-structured problem requiring reasoning about a wide range of interrelated variables such as the background knowledge that students bring into the classroom, teacher and student expectations about the content to be covered, and school and classroom guidelines and rules. Mendivil et al. (2022) pointed out that the use of technology in the classroom introduces a new set of variables into the teaching context and adds complexity due to its rapidly changing nature.

Table 1. Summary on the Level of Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Teachers

No	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Technological Knowledge	3.34	Moderately High
2	Pedagogical Knowledge	3.46	High
3	Content Knowledge	3.46	High
Overall Mean		3.42	High

3.2. Level of Instructional Practices of Teachers—Summary on the Level of Instructional Practices of Teachers

Table 2 provides a summary on the instructional practices of teachers. It is exhibited that the overall mean of the instructional practices of teachers is 3.92, which is in a high level. This means that the level of the instructional practices of teachers is oftentimes evident. Data show that the three (3) indicators have high level. As arranged chronologically, interpersonal has the highest mean score (4.18). This is followed by intrapersonal (4.16), and cognitive (3.43). These serve as proofs that the level of

instructional practices of teachers is oftentimes evident. The findings indicate that the overall instructional practices of teachers fall under the high-level category. This suggests that teachers consistently employ instructional strategies that support student learning across cognitive, interpersonal, and intrapersonal domains. The high overall mean reflects a strong commitment among teachers to engage students not just academically, but also socially and personally. It also implies that the instructional approaches used are effective in addressing diverse aspects of student development, promoting a holistic learning environment. A closer examination of

the three instructional practice domains reveals interpersonal strategies as the most prominent, followed closely by intrapersonal strategies, and cognitive strategies. These results imply that while teachers are particularly strong in fostering collaboration and self-directed learning, there is relatively less emphasis on higher-order thinking and problem-solving tasks. Strengthening cognitive practices, such as developing critical thinking, reasoning, and knowledge application, could further enhance instructional effectiveness. Overall, the data confirms that the instructional practices of teachers are not only consistent but also geared toward fostering comprehensive student growth. The high status of instructional practices of teachers supported the findings of Francisco and Celon (2020) disclosing that teachers use instructional strategies to help students become more independent and tactical learners. These strategies become effective learning strategies when students hand-picked the suitable ones and use them to complete tasks. Instructional strategies can stim-

ulate students and help them concentrate and merge information for understanding and remembering. Khanshan and Yousefi (2020) mentioned that another factor that is presumed to be conducive to the instructional practice of the teachers in the classroom is the expectancy of teachers in the learning skills and capacities of their learners. Furthermore, Yu et al. (2022) claimed that teacher’s belief about their own specialty and degree of knowledge can also impact the instructional practice. Expertise can be evaluated based on the instructional readiness. The teacher’s teaching experience influences instructional readiness, how much professional development a teacher has gained, teacher certification, and teacher readiness. Quality of teaching is not only impacted by teachers’ beliefs in their learners’ skills to learn but also in their beliefs about their own capacities to perform the lessons. Instructional practices generally refer to the teacher’s action in developing the lesson in the classroom.

Table 2. Summary on the Level of Instructional Practices of Teachers

No	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Cognitive	3.43	High
2	Interpersonal	4.18	High
3	Intrapersonal	4.16	High
Overall Mean		3.92	High

3.3. *Significance of the Relationship Between Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge and Instructional Practices of Teachers*—Presented in Table 3 are the data on the significance of the relationship between technological pedagogical content knowledge and instructional practices of teachers. Reflected in the hypothesis, the relationship was tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The overall r-value of .421 with a p-value of <0.05 signified the rejection of the null hypothesis. It means

that there is a significant relationship between technological pedagogical content knowledge and instructional practices of teachers. This shows that the technological pedagogical content knowledge of teachers is correlated with the instructional practices of teachers. Doing a pairwise correlation among the measures of both variables, it can be gleaned that technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, and content knowledge revealed computed r-values of 0.417, 0.425, and 0.420, respectively, with

p-values that were less than 0.05 in the level of significance. This implies that as technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, and content knowledge increase, the instructional practices of teachers also increase. The findings indicate a statistically significant positive relationship between technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) and the instructional

practices of teachers, as shown by an overall r-value of .421 and a p-value less than 0.05. This result leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis and confirmed that teachers' competency in integrating technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge is closely associated with the quality of their instructional practices.

Table 3. Significance of the Relationship Between Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge and Instructional Practices of Teachers

Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Teachers Indicators	Dependent Variable	r-value	p-value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Technological Knowledge	Instructional Practices of Teachers	0.417	0.000	Rejected	Moderate Strong Positive Correlation
Pedagogical Knowledge	Instructional Practices of Teachers	0.425	0.000	Rejected	
Content Knowledge	Instructional Practices of Teachers	0.420	0.000	Rejected	
Overall	Instructional Practices of Teachers	0.421*	0.000	Rejected	

Note. *Significant at 0.05 significance level.
 $r = .421 > .05$ — Moderate Strong Positive Correlation

The pairwise correlation analysis further supports this, with technological knowledge ($r = .417$), pedagogical knowledge ($r = .425$), and content knowledge ($r = .420$) each showing significant positive relationships with instructional practices. These findings suggest that improvements in any of the three components of TPACK are likely to result in enhanced teaching strategies, better classroom delivery, and more effective

engagement with students. These findings implied that educational institutions and policymakers must prioritize the development of teachers' TPACK through targeted professional development programs, workshops, and continuous learning opportunities. Teachers need structured support to effectively blend technology with appropriate pedagogical approaches and subject-specific knowledge, enabling them

to design instruction that is both innovative and aligned with curriculum goals. Teacher training institutions should also integrate TPACK into their preservice education curricula to ensure that future educators are well-equipped to navigate modern classrooms. Strengthening TPACK will not only improve instructional practices but also foster a more adaptive, student-centered learning environment that prepares learners for success in a digitally driven world. The significant relationship between technological pedagogical content knowledge and instructional practices of teachers supported the study of Ismaeel and Al Mulhim (2022), highlighting that technical competencies have also emerged as essential teacher qualifications. Apart from the knowledge and skills in using technology or Technological Knowledge (TK) to provide comprehensive learning, these technical competencies should also be developed amongst them. This confirms that the teacher's role as an educator will become more important. A teacher's ability to manage classes is primarily based on their mastery of Content Knowledge (CK). Additionally, the importance of mastering Pedagogical Knowledge (PK) and Technological Knowledge (TK) is recognized, with both integrated into Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (TPACK). Sierra et al. (2023) also noted that educators must possess high-level knowledge of technological competence, in addition to their existing content and pedagogical expertise, to achieve. Teachers must recognize that content-driven, pedagogically sound, and technologically forward-thinking knowledge is the greatest way to design teaching methods.

Hence, the hypothesis that there is no domain in technological pedagogical content knowledge of teachers that significantly influences the instructional practices of teachers is rejected. The regression analysis confirms that technological pedagogical content knowl-

Integrating technology is never about gaining mastery of technology. It is primarily about deciding the best combinations between content and pedagogy.

3.4. *Regression Analysis on Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge and Instructional Practices of Teachers*—Shown in table 4 is the regression analysis on technological pedagogical content knowledge and instructional practices of teachers. The overall p-value ($p < 0.05$) denotes that technological pedagogical content knowledge of teachers is a predictor of instructional practices of teachers. The B values of the independent variable, technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, and content knowledge is 0.423, 0.430, and 0.425 respectively. One unit change in technological knowledge will lead to .423-unit change in the instructional practices of teachers if the other predictor is at "0". In the same way, one unit change in pedagogical knowledge will lead to .430-unit change in instructional practices if the other predictor is at "0". Lastly, one unit change in content knowledge will lead to .425-unit change in instructional practices of teachers if the other predictor is at "0". Among the three, pedagogical knowledge indicates a higher influence on the instructional practices of teachers compared to other indicators. Lastly, the coefficient of determination of the R-squared value is also shown in the table, which was 0.177 or 17.7% of the instructional practices of teachers were explained by the domains of technological pedagogical content knowledge of teachers, which were technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, and content knowledge.

edge (TPACK) significantly predicts the instructional practices of teachers, as indicated by a p-value less than 0.05. The B values, 0.423 for technological knowledge, 0.430 for pedagogical knowledge, and 0.425 for content knowledge, demonstrate that each domain of TPACK

Table 4. Regression Analysis on Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge and Instructional Practices of Teachers

Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Teachers	(Standardized Coefficients)	B (Unstandardized Coefficients)	t	Sig.
Constant	–	0.431	6.160	0.000
Technological Knowledge	0.423	0.444	6.340	0.000
Pedagogical Knowledge	0.430	0.451	6.440	0.000
Content Knowledge	0.425	0.446	6.370	0.000
Model Statistics	$r = 0.421$			
	$R^2 = 0.177$			
	$F = 23.45$			
	$p = 0.000$			

individually contributes to the improvement of instructional practices. Notably, pedagogical knowledge has the highest influence, suggesting that a teacher’s understanding of effective teaching methods plays a slightly more dominant role in shaping instructional performance. This means that even when other variables are held constant, enhancing pedagogical knowledge results in the most substantial improvement in how teachers deliver instruction, followed closely by content and technological knowledge. The implication of these findings is that professional development initiatives for teachers should give strong emphasis to strengthening pedagogical competencies while also integrating training in technological and content knowledge. Although TPACK as a whole contributes to 17.7% of the variance in instructional practices, this figure highlights the value of these domains while also indicating that other factors may be influencing teaching performance and should be explored further. Educational leaders and teacher training institutions should therefore adopt a holistic approach that not only improves TPACK but

also examines complementary elements such as classroom management, motivation, and learner diversity. By focusing on these critical areas, schools can better support teachers in becoming well-rounded, effective educators in a rapidly evolving educational landscape. The findings of the study align with the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge Framework by Mishra and Koeler (2006) as cited by Kurt (2018). This framework focuses on technological knowledge (TK), pedagogical knowledge (PK), and content knowledge (CK), offers a productive approach to many of the dilemmas that teachers face in implementing educational technology (edtech) in their classrooms. By differentiating among these three types of knowledge, the TPACK framework outlines how content (what is being taught) and pedagogy (how the teacher imparts that content) must form the foundation for any effective edtech integration. This order is important because the technology being implemented must communicate the content and support the pedagogy in order to enhance students’ learning experience. The TPACK Framework is highly relevant to understanding the relation-

ship between Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) and the instructional practices of teachers, as it provides a structured approach to integrating technology effectively into teaching. It emphasizes the interconnectedness of three core knowledge areas—content, pedagogy, and technology—and highlights how their synergy enhances instructional design and delivery. By applying the TPACK framework,

teachers can make informed decisions on selecting and using digital tools that align with subject-specific content and pedagogical strategies, creating more engaging and compelling learning experiences. This relevance is particularly critical in today's education landscape, where technology plays an integral role in addressing diverse learning needs and fostering student achievement.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

Presented in this chapter are the findings based on the results of data gathered, the conclusions drawn from the findings, and the recommendations for consideration.

4.1. Findings—The primary focus of the study was to determine the significance of the relationship between technological pedagogical content knowledge and instructional practices of teachers in public elementary schools. The study was conducted in the selected elementary schools in Matina District, Davao City Division. There were one hundred eleven (111) elementary teachers who participated in this study. A descriptive correlational method of research was used in this study, utilizing adopted research instruments. The said instruments were validated by the panel of experts and subjected to pilot testing before it was made ready for administration. Mean, Pearson Product Correlation of Coefficient, and Regression Analysis were the statistical tools used in analyzing the data. The hypotheses raised in this study were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The level of technological pedagogical content knowledge of teachers is high. This suggests that educators are well-equipped to integrate technology effectively with their teaching practices. It further indicates that teachers possess a strong understanding of how to blend content knowledge with pedagogical strategies and technological tools, which is crucial for adapting to modern teaching environments. Consequently, teachers with high TPACK are better positioned to

enhance student engagement and learning outcomes through innovative and dynamic instructional practices. Meanwhile, the level of instructional practices of teachers is high. This suggests that educators are consistently employing effective teaching strategies and methods in their classrooms. It further indicates that teachers are likely adapting their approaches to meet the diverse needs of students, fostering an environment conducive to learning. As a result, high instructional practices contribute to positive student engagement, performance, and overall classroom dynamics. It was found out that there is a significant relationship between technological pedagogical content knowledge and instructional practices of teachers. The finding indicates that teachers' ability to effectively integrate technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge directly impacts their teaching methods. This suggests that when teachers enhance their understanding and application of TPACK, their instructional practices improve, leading to more engaging and effective lessons. Furthermore, the significant relationship underscores the importance of continuous professional development in strengthening teachers' TPACK to optimize their instructional performance. More so, it was revealed that all the domains of technological pedagogical content knowledge sig-

nificantly influence the instructional practices of teachers. This highlights the comprehensive role that technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge play in shaping effective teaching methods. Each domain contributes to enhancing teachers' ability to deliver high-quality instruction, demonstrating the interconnectedness of technology, pedagogy, and subject matter expertise. This suggests that professional development programs should address all three TPACK domains to fully equip teachers with the skills needed to improve their teaching practices.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were offered: The level of technological pedagogical content knowledge of teachers is high which means that it was oftentimes evident. Notably, pedagogical knowledge and content knowledge were oftentimes evident while technological knowledge is occasionally evident. Meanwhile, the level of instructional practices of teachers is high. In particular, all indicators, namely, cognitive, interpersonal, and intrapersonal are oftentimes evident. Based on the findings, technological pedagogical content knowledge and instructional practices of teachers are related. In fact, all domains of technological pedagogical content knowledge are linked to the instructional practices of teachers. Also, technological pedagogical content knowledge significantly influenced the instructional practices of teachers. In fact, all domains of technological pedagogical content knowledge, namely, technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, and content knowledge, significantly influence the instructional practices of teachers by registering a p-value of .000, which is less than .05 in the level of significance. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Further, the result indicates that for every unit increase in the three domains of technological pedagogical content knowledge, the instructional practices of teachers will also increase. Moreover, pedagogical

knowledge was the indicator that significantly influences the instructional practices of teachers the most. The significant and moderate positive correlation between the technological pedagogical content knowledge and instructional practices of teachers supports the principles established in the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge Framework by Mishra and Koeler (2006). The framework focuses on designing and evaluating teacher knowledge that is concentrated on effective student learning in various content areas. Thus, TPACK is a useful frame for thinking about what knowledge teachers must have to integrate technology into teaching and how they might develop this knowledge. Using TPACK as a framework for measuring teaching knowledge could potentially have an impact on the type of training and professional development experiences that are designed for both preservice and in-service teachers.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the findings of the study, several recommendations are proposed to address the identified issues and enhance current practices. These recommendations aim to promote informed decisions and continuous improvement. The following suggestions were offered based on the conclusions of the study: DepEd Officials Based on the findings, it is recommended that DepEd officials prioritize the continuous professional development of teachers by offering targeted training programs that enhance all three domains of technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK), with a particular focus on strengthening technological knowledge. Since pedagogical knowledge was identified as having the most significant impact on instructional practices, DepEd should ensure that teachers have access to in-depth, ongoing workshops that focus on effective teaching strategies and the integration of technology. Additionally, DepEd may implement initiatives that support the integration of technology into the curriculum, making it accessible for teachers to enhance their instruc-

tional practices. By investing in comprehensive TPACK development, DepEd may further improve teaching quality, ensuring that teachers are equipped to meet the diverse needs of students in a modern, technology-driven classroom environment. School Heads Moreover, school heads may prioritize providing teachers with professional development opportunities that enhance their technological knowledge, as this domain was noted to be occasionally evident compared to pedagogical and content knowledge. Since pedagogical knowledge was found to have the most significant influence on instructional practices, school heads may also focus on fostering a culture of continuous pedagogical improvement through workshops and collaborative learning environments. Additionally, school heads may encourage the integration of technology in the classroom by providing teachers with the necessary tools and resources, as well as offering training that supports the seamless combination of technology, pedagogy, and content. By strengthening all three areas of technological pedagogical content knowledge, school heads may significantly enhance the quality and effectiveness of instructional practices across the school. Teachers Furthermore, teachers are encouraged to continue strengthening their technological knowledge to complement their already strong pedagogical and content knowl-

edge. Since pedagogical knowledge was found to have the most significant impact on instructional practices, teachers may prioritize refining their teaching strategies, ensuring they are up-to-date with best practices in pedagogy. Additionally, teachers may seek out professional development opportunities that integrate technology into teaching, as enhancing technological knowledge can further improve instructional practices and better engage students in the learning process. By focusing on these areas, teachers may create more dynamic, effective, and adaptable classroom environments.

Future Researchers Lastly, future researchers are encouraged to explore the underlying factors that contribute to the occasionally evident technological knowledge among teachers, as identified in the study, to better understand the barriers to fully integrating technology into instructional practices. Additionally, further investigation may be conducted into how pedagogical knowledge, which was found to have the most significant influence on instructional practices, can be effectively developed and supported through professional development programs. Researchers may also examine the long-term impact of enhancing all three domains of technological pedagogical content knowledge on student outcomes.

5. References

- AACTE Committee on Innovation and Technology. (2008). *Handbook of technological pedagogical content knowledge (tpck) for educators*. Routledge. <https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation?paperid=110912>
- Ahmed, M. (2022). Business english instruction: Empowering learners with the 4cs of the 21st century. *Frontiers in Education*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/education/articles/10.3389/feduc.2022.998987/full>
- Ajani, O. (2024). Technological pedagogical content knowledge for twenty-first-century learning skills. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*. <https://ssbfnet.com/ojs/index.php/ijrbs/article/view/3355>

- Akun, J., & Mohamad, F. (2020). Technological pedagogical content knowledge (tpack) and the teaching of science: Determiners for professional development. *Educacion y Educadores*, 39(1). <https://doi.org/10.25115/eea.v39i1.4272>
- Alanazi, F., et al. (2023). Science teachers' perceptions of the cultural factors influencing students' science learning: Comparative analysis of saudi arabia, egypt, and yemen. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/374349658>
- Algonos, C., Calizo, E., & Bauyot, M. (2024). Experiences of teachers teaching in far-flung areas of the division of davao del norte: A phenomenological study. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*. <https://rsisinternational.org/journals/ijriss/articles/experiences-of-teachers-teaching-in-far-flung-areas-of-division-of-davao-del-norte-a-phenomenological-study/>
- Aliustaoglu, F., & Tuna, A. (2022). Analysis of the pedagogical content knowledge development of prospective teachers in the lesson plan development process: 4mat model. *International Journal of Progressive Education*. <https://ijpe.inased.org/makale/2932>
- Alkalaki, E. (2021). Pedagogical content knowledge: A comparative study of greek heritage language teachers in sweden. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2:1566325>
- Amiruddin, S. K. (2023). Issues and challenges in teacher education in india: An analytical study. <https://doi.org/10.2017/IJRCS/202303003>
- Andoh, N., et al. (2022). Assessment of technological pedagogical content knowledge of senior high school business teachers in the central region, ghana. <https://ijssers.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/05-1310-2022.pdf>
- Asomah, R., Agyei, D., & Ntow, F. (2023). Developing in-service mathematics teachers' pedagogical content knowledge and skills to teach trigonometry: Using a cooperative teaching and learning approach. <https://www.conmaths.com/>
- Azad, S., Asadollahfam, H., & Zoghi, M. (2021). The contribution of teachers' interpersonal behaviors to learners' autonomous and controlled motivation. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1299261.pdf>
- Barbour, M. K., & Hodges, C. B. (2024). Preparing teachers to teach online: A critical issue for teacher education. <https://www.learntechlib.org/primary/p/223927>
- Beardsley, M., Albó, L., Aragón, P., & Hernández-Leo, D. (2021). Emergency education effects on teacher abilities and motivation to use digital technologies. *British Journal of Educational Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.13101>
- Beri, N., & Sharma, L. (2021). Development of tpack for teacher-educators: A technological pedagogical content knowledge scale. *Linguistics and Culture Review*. <https://doi.org/10.21744/lingcure.v5nS1.1646>
- Bhatpahari. (2021). The relevance of rawlsian justice in india. <https://scholar.google.com.ph/scholar>
- Blazar & Polard. (2022). Measuring good teaching is complicated. <https://www.nctq.org/research-insights/measuring-good-teaching-is-complicated>
- Bueno, R., et al. (2023). Technological pedagogical content knowledge: Exploring new perspectives. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*. <https://ajet.org.au/index.php/AJET/article/download/7970/1976/28285>

- Bui, T. (2022). English teachers' integration of digital technologies in the classroom. *Social Sciences Humanities Open*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666374022000802>
- Caires, S., et al. (2023). Promoting socio-emotional skills in initial teacher training: An emotional educational programme. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/5cc1/5bc795ba44d6d9e6f4433643d7012459c9aa.pdf>
- Cansiz, M. (2021). Investigating the technological pedagogical content knowledge of preservice teachers. *Science Education Review*. <https://serd.artvin.edu.tr/tr/download/article-file/850921>
- Chen, F., & Abdullah, R. B. (2022). Teacher cognition and practice of educational equity in english as a foreign language teaching. *Frontiers in Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.820042>
- Chen, X., & Vibulphol, J. (2019). An exploration of motivational strategies and factors that affect strategies: A case of chinese efl teachers. *International Education Studies*, 12(11), 47–55. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ies.v12n11p47>
- Chi, C. (2023). *Learning poverty in the philippines linked to poor teaching quality – world bank study* [Accessed: 2025-07-06]. <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2023/09/22/2298233/learning-poverty-philippines-linked-poor-teaching-quality-world-bank-study>
- Clores, L., & Espana, R. (2023). Assessment of teachers' instructional practices: Towards proposing an innovative instructional model for teaching-learning material in chemistry. *ERIC*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ej1400660.pdf>
- Coristine, S., Russo, S., Fitzmorris, R., Beninato, P., & Rivolta, G. (2022). The importance of student-teacher relationships. classroom practice in 2022.
- Den Brok, P., Tartwijk, J., & Mainhard, T. (2023). Effective interpersonal relationships: On the association between teacher agency and communion with student outcomes. *Wageningen University Research Publications*. <https://research.wur.nl/en/publications/effective-interpersonal-relationships-on-the-association-between->
- Dewi, N., et al. (2021). Technological, pedagogical, content knowledge (tpack) research trends: A systematic literature review of publications between 2010 and 2020. *ERIC*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1339464.pdf>
- Dickerson, C. (2022). Using a teacher knowledge framework to connect teaching practice with theory. *Journal of Education for Teaching*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/25783858.2022.2115942>
- Dizon, R., Calbi, J., Cuyos, J., & Miranda, M. (2019). Perspectives on the implementation of the k to 12 program in the philippines: A research review. *International Journal of Innovation and Research in Educational Science*, 6, 757–765.
- Dogan, S., Dogan, N., & Celik, I. (2020). Teachers' skills to integrate technology in education: Two path models explaining instructional and application software use. <https://d-nb.info/1219622702/34>
- Donnelly, A., et al. (2019). Inspiring inclusion in your classroom and beyond. *ERIC*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1245095.pdf>
- Duan, G., Jia, L., & Chen, H. (2022). The role of english as a foreign language teachers' technological pedagogical content knowledge on english as a foreign language students' achievement. *Frontiers in Psychology*. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9274087/>

- Elsayary, A. (2023). The impact of a professional upskilling training program on developing teachers' digital competence. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcal.12788>
- Falcon, S., Admiraal, W., & Leon, J. (2023). Teachers' engaging messages are linked to students' performance and teachers' enthusiasm. *Learning and Instruction*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0959475223000191>
- Filgona, J., John, S., & Gwany, D. (2020). Teachers' pedagogical content knowledge and students' academic achievement: A theoretical overview. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344199882>
- Fletcher, T. (2021). Pedagogical principles that support the prioritisation of meaningful experiences in physical education: Conceptual and practical considerations. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17408989.2021.1884672>
- Francisco, C., & Celon, L. (2020). Teachers' instructional practices and their effects on students' academic performance.
- Fukaya, T., Fukuda, M., & Suzuki, M. (2024). Relationship between mathematical pedagogical content knowledge, beliefs, and motivation of elementary school teachers. *Frontiers in Education*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2023.1276439>
- Galindo, J. (2023). Technological pedagogical and content knowledge (tpack) assessment of basic education teachers in st. paul university surigao. *Cognizance: Journal of Research*, 3(6). <https://cognizancejournal.com/vol3issue6/V3I635.pdf>
- Ghafoor, N., & Rabaia, S. (2022). Stimulants of cognitive strategies: The most prominent types & importance of using in the teaching and learning process (a survey study of the relevant literature). *International Journal of Higher Education*, 11(2), 30–37. <https://ideas.repec.org/a/jfr/ijhe11/v11y2022i2p30.html>
- Gorter, D., & Arocena, E. (2020). Teachers' beliefs about multilingualism in a course on translanguaging. *System*, 92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2020.102275>
- Greene, M., Cheng, S., & Jones, M. (2023). Preservice teachers' technology integration knowledge development in an online technology-based course. *International Journal of Instruction*, 16(4), 397–416. https://www.e-iji.net/dosyalar/iji_2023_4_23.pdf
- Groenewald, E. (2024). Teacher professional identity: Agentic actions of a novice teacher in a challenging school context. *Teachers and Teaching*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13540602.2024.2308890>
- Gumarang Jr., B. K., & Gumarang, B. K. (2021). Unraveling deterioration in the quality of philippine education. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*, 2(10), 914–917. <https://doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.02.10.08>
- Hair, J. F., et al. (2018). Pls-sem or cb-sem: Updated guidelines on which method to use [Available at Google Scholar].
- Haleem, A., et al. (2022). Understanding the role of digital technologies in education: A review. *Education and Information Technologies*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666412722000137>
- Haron, M., et al. (2021). Examining the teachers' pedagogical knowledge and learning facilities towards teaching quality. *Education Review*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1285877.pdf>
- Hegwood, V. (2023). The top 10 biggest challenges teachers face in the classroom today.

- Ilyas, M., & Zaman, S. (2023). An empirical enquiry into the teachers' philosophical beliefs and their actual classroom practices: A case of Pakistan. *Journal of Pedagogical Research*. <http://journalppw.com/>
- Jeschke, C., et al. (2021). Teachers' ability to apply their subject-specific knowledge in instructional settings—a qualitative comparative study in the subjects mathematics and economics. *Frontiers in Education*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2021.683962>
- Jiatong, W., et al. (2024). Impact of passion at work on emotional exhaustion: Mediating role of negative emotions. *Journal of Affective Disorders*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/383493111>
- Kang, S. (2024). Applying cognitive psychology to improve learning: Current developments and future directions. *Applied Cognitive Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/mac0000196>
- Khanshan, S., & Yousefi, M. (2020). The relationship between self-efficacy and instructional practice of in-service soft disciplines, hard disciplines, and EFL teachers. *Asian-Pacific Journal of Second and Foreign Language Education*. <https://sfleducation.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s40862-020-0080-8>
- Kurt, S. (2018). TPACK: Technological pedagogical content knowledge framework.
- La Velle, L. (2023). Development of teachers' knowledge: The breadth, depth, and detail. *Journal of Education for Teaching*. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/02607476.2023.2245219>
- Lave, J., & Wenger, E. (1991). *Situated learning: Legitimate peripheral participation*. Cambridge University Press.
- Lee, H., Chung, C., & Wei, G. (2022). Research on technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge: A bibliometric analysis from 2011 to 2020. *Frontiers in Education*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/education/articles/10.3389/feduc.2022.765233/full>
- Leedy, P., & Ormrod, J. (2019). *Practical research: Planning and design* (12th ed.) [PDF available e.g. via b-ok.org]. Pearson.
- Leijen, A. (2022). What constitutes teachers' general pedagogical knowledge and how it can be assessed: A literature review. *Teachers and Teaching*. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/13540602.2022.2062710>
- Magallanes, K., Chung, J. Y., & Lee, S. (2022). The Philippine teachers' concerns on educational reform using a concern-based adoption model. *Frontiers in Education*, 7, 763991. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2022.763991>
- Mendivil, C., Laca, A., Bra, & de la Cruz, J. (2022). Technological pedagogical content knowledge: Implementation of a didactic proposal for preservice history teachers. *Frontiers in Education*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/feduc.2022.852801/full>
- Mishra, M., et al. (2022). Integration of technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) in classrooms through a teacher's lens. *International Journal of Humanities Studies*. <https://sciencescholar.us/journal/index.php/ijhs/article/view/9536>
- Mishra, P., & Koehler, M. J. (2006). Technological pedagogical content knowledge: A framework for integrating technology in teachers' knowledge. *Teachers College Record*, 108(6), 1017–1054.
- Molina, E., Fatima, S. F., Ho, A. D., Melo, C., Wilichowski, T. M., & Pushparatnam, A. (2020). Measuring the quality of teaching practices in primary schools: Assessing the validity

- of the teach observation tool in punjab, pakistan. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 96, 103171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2020.103171>
- Munoz, E., et al. (2020). Intrapersonal skills and music performance in elementary piano students in spanish conservatories: Three case studies. *International Journal of Music Education*. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0255761419873782>
- Musgrove, A., Powers, J., Nichols, B., & Lapp, S. (2021). Exploring the role of elementary teachers' tpack in the adoption of 1:1 computing across subject areas. *Contemporary Issues in Technology and Teacher Education*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1330700.pdf>
- Noor, A., Jasmi, K., Shukor, K., Khalid, N., Razak, M., Rahman, M., & Basir, M. (2020). The elements of intrapersonal skills practiced among excellent lecturers of islamic education in malaysian polytechnics. *Journal of Critical Reviews*. <https://www.jcreview.com/admin/Uploads/Files/61bf8697a07a06.07374488.pdf>
- Nugal, R., Morales, J., Dayday, R. S., & Cubero, G. (2023). Technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge of college teachers and its influence on the academic performance of pre-service teachers. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*. <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=20527>
- Nyakito, C., Amimo, C., & Allida, V. (2021). Challenges of integrating information and communication technology in teaching among national teachers' colleges in uganda. *East African Journal of Education and Social Sciences*, 2(3). <https://doi.org/10.46606/eajess2021v02i03.0114>
- Okwuduba, E., Nwosu, K., Okigbo, E., Samuel, N., & Achugbu, C. (2021). Impact of intrapersonal and interpersonal emotional intelligence and self-directed learning on academic performance among pre-university science students. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/350516738>
- Orakova, A., Nametkulova, F., Issayeva, G., Mukhambetzhanova, S., Galimzhanova, M., & Rezuanova, G. (2024). The relationships between pedagogical and technological competence and the digital literacy level of teachers. *Journal of Curriculum Studies Research*. <https://doi.org/10.46303/jcsr.2024.2>
- Piper, S. (2019). *Upper elementary teachers' use of pedagogical content knowledge with nonfiction reading instruction* [Doctoral dissertation, Walden University]. <https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=8457&context=dissertations>
- Putri, A., Pahlevi, M., & Wachyudi, K. (2023). Efl novice teachers' beliefs and practice on teaching grammar: A case study of novice teachers in junior high school. *Innovative: Journal of Social Science Research*. <https://j-innovative.org/index.php/innovative>
- Quast, J., Rubach, C., & Porsch, R. (2023). Professional digital competence beliefs of student teachers, pre-service teachers and teachers: Validating an instrument based on the dig-compedu framework. *European Journal of Teacher Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2023.2251663>
- Ragab, M. A., & Arisha, A. (2018). Research methodology in business: A starter's guide. *Management and Organizational Studies*, 5(1), 1–14.
- Rajiha, N. (2022). Technological pedagogical and content knowledge (tpack) of in-service english teachers in pati, central java, indonesia. *INCoILS: International Conference on Islamic and Language Studies*. <https://incoils.or.id/index.php/INCOILS/article/download/83/63/68v>

- Saleh, S., & Jing, T. A. (2020). Instructional practices in science education in German and Malaysian secondary schools: A comparative case study. *International Journal of Instruction*, 13(4), 267–282. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iji.2020.13417a>
- Santos, J., & Castro, R. (2021). Technological pedagogical content knowledge (tpack) in action: Application of learning in the classroom by pre-service teachers (pst). *Education and Information Technologies*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2590291121000061>
- Sarkar, M., Gutierrez-Bucheli, L., Lazarus, M., Wright, C., White, P., & Ilic, D. (2024). Pedagogical content knowledge (pck) in higher education: A systematic scoping review. *Teaching and Teacher Education*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0742051X24001409>
- Schmid, M., Brianza, E., & Petko, D. (2020). Developing a short assessment instrument for technological pedagogical content knowledge (tpack.xs) and comparing the factor structure of an integrative and a transformative model. *Computers & Education*, 157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2020.103967>
- Schmid, M., Brianza, E., & Petko, D. (2021). Self-reported technological pedagogical content knowledge (tpack) of pre-service teachers about digital technology use in lesson plans. *Computers in Human Behavior*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0747563220303332>
- Schmidt, D. A., Baran, E., Thompson, A. D., Mishra, P., Koehler, M. J., & Shin, T. S. (2009). Technological pedagogical content knowledge (tpack): The development and validation of an assessment instrument for preservice teachers. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 42(2), 123–149. <https://scholar.google.com.ph/scholar>
- Sergeeva, O. V., Zheltukhina, M., Sizova, Z., Ishuradiva, A., Khlusyanov, O., & Kalashnikova, E. (2024). Exploring pre-service teachers' ICT competence beliefs. *Contemporary Educational Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.30935/cedtech/14331>
- Shah, K. (2020). Learner-centred teaching and related instructional practices.
- Shambare, B., & Simuja, C. (2024). Mapping tpack competency among life sciences teachers in rural and marginalised secondary schools: A descriptive analysis. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/385728475>
- Shumeiko, T., Bezhina, V., Zhiyenbayeva, A., & Bozhevolnaya, N. (2024). Improving the readiness of teachers for using distance technologies in supplementary technical education: A case study in Kazakhstan. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Scientific Studies*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.53894/ijirss.v7i1.2506>
- Sierra, A., Cabero-Almanera, J., Iglesias, J., & Palacios-Rodríguez, A. (2023). Development of the teacher's technological pedagogical content knowledge (tpack) from the lesson study: A systematic review. *Frontiers in Education*, 8, 1078913. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/educ.2023.1078913/full>
- Soko, I., & Samo, D. (2023). The analysis of in-service teachers' practices of implementing technological pedagogical content knowledge (tpack). *European Journal of Education*. <https://www.ej-edu.org/index.php/ejedu/article/view/585>
- Sreekumar, D. (2024). What is correlational research: Definition, types, and examples.

- Sugesti, I., et al. (2019). Teachers' cognition and their teaching practices in an efl classroom: A correlational study. *Proceedings of the International Seminar on Education Technology (ISET-19)*. <https://www.atlantis-press.com/proceedings/iset-19/125941475>
- Tallman, M. (2023). What makes pedagogical content knowledge “pedagogical”? reconnecting pck to its deweyan foundations. *Education Resources Information Center (ERIC)*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1398481.pdf>
- Tang, K. (2023). Student-centered approach in teaching and learning: What does it mean? *Asian Pacific Journal of Academics*, 2(2). <https://doi.org/10.53623/apga.v2i2.218>
- Tapis, A. (2022). Planning and implementing technology in the primary classroom: A study of chilean student teachers' pedagogic development. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/359316998>
- Tasar, M., & Ergul, Y. (2023). Technological pedagogical content knowledge (tpack) in physics education. *AIP Conference Proceedings*. https://doi.org/10.1063/9780735425712_001
- Tawfik, A. A., Shepherd, C. E., Gatewood, J., & Gish-Lieberman, J. J. (2021). First and second-order barriers to teaching in k-12 online learning. *TechTrends*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11528-021-00648-y>
- Theledi, O. (2024). Teachers' pedagogical content knowledge and subject matter content knowledge: Is the framework still relevant in teaching stem? <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/380352329>
- Thomas, L. (2020). Cluster sampling: A simple step-by-step guide with examples.
- Tian, L., & Shen, J. (2023). The effect of perceived teachers' interpersonal behavior on students' learning in physical education: A systematic review. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/373494330>
- Valente, S., Lourenco, A., & Nemeth, Z. (2020). School conflicts: Causes and management strategies in classroom relationships. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/347936512_School_conflicts_Causes_and_management_strategies_in_classroom_relationships
- Vanner, C. (2022). Elements and impacts of student-teacher relationships. In *Foundations of teaching and learning*. <https://ecampusontario.pressbooks.pub/educ5202/chapter/elements-and-impacts-of-student-teacher-relationships/>
- Verhoef, P., Broekhuizen, T., Bhattacharya, A., Ding, J., Fabian, N., & Haenlein, M. (2021). Digital transformation: A multidisciplinary reflection and research agenda. *Journal of Business Research*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0148296319305478>
- Walan, S. (2020). Embracing digital technology in science classrooms: Secondary school teachers' enacted teaching and reflections on practice. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 29, 431–441. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10956-020-09828-6>
- Yang, M., Jeyaraj, J., Ahmad, N., & Yang, W. (2024). Characteristics of chinese higher education efl teachers' behaviors based on technological pedagogical content knowledge (tpack). <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/385480230>
- Yik, B., Stains, M., Johnson, E., Raker, J., Henderson, C., Apkarian, N., & Dancy, M. (2022). Association of malleable factors with adoption of research-based instructional strategies in introductory chemistry, mathematics, and physics. *Frontiers in Education*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/education/articles/10.3389/feduc.2022.1016415/full>

- Yu, J., Kreijkes, P., & Aro, K. (2022). Students' growth mindset: Relation to teacher beliefs, teaching practices, and school climate. *Learning and Individual Differences*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0959475222000378>
- Zhang, Q. (2022). The role of teachers' interpersonal behaviors in learners' academic achievements. *Frontiers in Psychology*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychology/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.921832/full>
- Zhang, W., & Tang, J. (2021). Teachers' track development: A review of literature. *Creative Education*, 12(5), 1074–1090. <https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation?paperid=110813>
- Zhang, Y. (2022). Developing efl teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge through practices in a virtual platform. *Frontiers in Psychology*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychology/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.916060/full>